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Corresponding Author:
Abhishek Kumar
abhishekg.agri@gmail.com

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POPULAR ARTICLE

Nematode Management: Options and Constraints for Organic Agriculture

Abhishek Kumar^{1*}, Priyanka Yadav¹, Ajay Kumar Mishra¹, Amit Kumar Yadav¹, Shivani Chaudhary¹ and Rohit Gangwar²

¹Department of Plant Pathology, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University of Agriculture and Technology, Meerut-250110, India

²Department of Floriculture, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University of Agriculture and Technology, Meerut-250110, India

ABSTRACT

*Plant-parasitic nematodes (PPNs) are obligate parasites that feed mainly on plant roots with common aboveground symptoms of stunting, yellowing, wilting, yield losses, and belowground root malformation due to direct feeding damage. Nematodes are unsegmented, bilaterally symmetric roundworms, usually microscopic, and taper toward both head and tail, but females of some of the species may be pear, lemon, or kidney-shaped. Feeding of many PPNs creates entryways into plant roots for secondary pathogens, while feeding of some species directly transmits plant viruses. Nematodes of greatest importance in organic crops appear to be sedentary endoparasites in the family Heteroderidae including the cyst nematodes (e.g., species of *Heterodera* and *Globodera*) and root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.), and migratory endoparasites of family *Pratylenchidae* (*Pratylenchus* spp.). Cyst nematode species including soybean cyst, potato cyst, and cereal cyst nematodes cause huge crop losses*

Keywords: nematodes, roots, potato, crop, food, plants .

INTRODUCTION

Cyst nematode-infected plants may develop a bushy roots system, and individual roots may have knotted appearance with several females at each knot. Root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are economically important polyphagous obligate plant parasites, distributed worldwide, and are known to parasitize nearly every plant species of higher plants [11, 17, 26]. As a result of the feeding of root-knot nematode, small to large galls or “knots” can form throughout the root system of infected plants. In contrast, lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus* spp.) are migratory endoparasites and feed within the root system. All major food crops are damaged by at least one species of nematodes, and the economic consequences of nematode infestations are many and varied, reducing crop quality and yield [13]. Organic farming has increased significantly worldwide over the last several years and is expected to grow further [12]. Organic farming is a set of plant and animal production practices that emphasize reliance on sustainable and renewable biological processes.

Limited information is available on PPN densities and their damage in organic farming systems. Therefore, to illustrate the potential for nematode damage and opportunities or constraints for their management in organic agriculture

Nematode Management: Options and Constraints for Organic Agriculture

Basic methods of nematode management are exclusion, eradication,

and protection [13,1]. Plant protection in organic agriculture, however, relies primarily on creating a favourable ecological equilibrium among soil biota without the use of synthetic pesticides [2]. Methods for nematode management, application of organic amendments, cover crops, crop rotation, nematode trap crops, antagonistic crops, and biological control.

Soil Organic Amendments

The effects of amendments in general are accepted as indirectly causing the nematode suppression through enhanced activity of naturally occurring antagonists (such as bacteria, fungi, and predatory nematodes) [14]. Various antagonistic fungi and bacteria have been observed in compost including species of *Trichoderma*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Pantoea*, and *Actinomycetes* [7] which help control soil-borne pathogens and PPNs. Additionally, plant residues and other organic amendments such as composted animal manure may release nematicidal compounds such as ammonia directly lethal to nematodes.

Nematode-suppressive crops (Trap cropping)

Another effective, non-chemical practice for managing nematodes involves the planting of crops that will suppress the development of these soil pests. Such crops reduce nematode populations in soil by depriving them of food or by releasing chemicals into the soil that inhibit their reproduction and development. Nematode-suppressive crops include marigolds, chrysanthemums, castor bean, partridge pea, velvet bean, vetch, rapeseed, and sesame.

Antagonistic crops

- a. Certain crops like mustard, marigold and neem, etc. have chemicals or alkaloids as root exudates which repel or suppress the plant-parasitic nematodes.
- b. In marigold (*Tagetes* spp.) plants the α - terthinyl and bithinyl compounds are present throughout the plant from root to shoot tips. This chemical kills the nematodes.
- c. In mustard allyl isothiocyanate and in pangolagrasyrocaterchol are present

which kills the nematodes.

Such enemy plants can be grown along with the main crop or included in crop rotation.

Animal Manures

Composted animal manure is one of the most popular organic amendments for soils. Poultry or livestock manure has been tested for nematode management. Numerous studies have found positive correlations between the addition of compost and suppression of PPNs including the economically important species such as root-knot and root-lesion nematodes.

Crop Rotation

Planting non-host crops in the rotation would remove the food source for the PPNs and consequently decline in their population below the damaging levels. However, the effectiveness of rotation in suppressing the PPN population depends upon the type of the nematode species present in the field, the host range, and the duration of time pest nematode can survive in the field in the absence of the host [4]. In general, for specialized host-specific plant-parasitic nematode (such as root-knot and cyst nematodes species) selection of non-host crops is relatively less difficult as compared to the nematode with a wider host range (such as root-lesion nematode). Nevertheless, accurate identification of plant-parasitic nematode/s prevalent in the field would help in selecting a non-host crop and planning a long-term rotation with a focus on nematode management in organic farming.

Deep summer ploughing

Deep summer ploughing of root-knot infested fields during the month of May-June particularly in the north- West India is followed to expose the nematodes in soil and infected tissue to solar heat and dehydration; this practice has been found to be effective for the management of root-knot nematodes. For raising small nursery beds for vegetable crops like tomato and brinjal seed beds can be prepared during summer, covered with polythene sheets which enhance soil temperature by 5 to 10°C which kills the nematodes in the seed bed. This method is very effective and nematode-free seedlings can be raised by soil solarization

using polythene sheets.

Soil solarisation

Another way that can be used to reduce RKN damage is by using a process called soil solarisation. Solarization is usually done in mid-summer to maximize soil heating effects. The soil is covered with plastic film for at least 2 weeks and this killed the egg of the nematode, thus reducing the population of RKN. The most successful use of soil solarization takes place in heavier (loamy to clay soils) rather than sandy soils. Soils with good water holding capacity enhance the heat transfer to deeper soil horizons. Therefore, soil depth affected the number of RKN killed in the roots. For effective soil solarization, moist the soil, then cover it with a transparent plastic sheet. Leave the sheet in place for 4 to 6 weeks during the June to mid July. Root-knot nematodes, including eggs, die when soil temperature exceeds 125°F for 30 minutes or 130°F for 5 minutes.

Biological Control

Microbial pathogens, endophytes, and antagonists are important in the regulation of PPNs, independent of the farming system [8,5,22]. However, the introduction of beneficial organisms to the soil for nematode management via augmentative biological control has had limited success [20]. There are few commercial biological control products for nematode management available in the market that might be considered for use in organic farming.

Bacterial Pathogens and Antagonists

Several types of saprophytic bacteria are antagonistic to nematodes, with their unique modes of action. *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. sphaericus*, and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* produce metabolites toxic to PPNs. Many different mechanisms have been proposed for nematode control by rhizobacteria including direct antagonism through the release of nitrogenous compounds toxic to nematodes, induced systemic resistance, and interference with plant– nematode recognition, and plant growth promotion. *Pasteuria* are parasites of all the economically important genera of PPNs. *Pasteuria penetrans*, parasitic on root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) [18,22], high application rates of *Pasteuria*-based products

are necessary for achieving effective nematode control, it may still not be cost-effective to apply at large-scale cropping areas [21].

Fungal Pathogens and Antagonists

A wide range of fungi is known to parasitize PPNs and possess the potential for biological control of nematodes [8,23,9,19,20,22]. *Dactylella* spp., *Dactylaria candida*, *Arthrobotrys botryospora*, *Paecilomyces liliacinus*, *Verticillium chlamydosporium*, and *Hirsutella hirsutella* possess the potential to be developed into biological control products [5,22]. Obligate fungal parasites species such as *Catenaria auxiliaris* and *Nematophthoragynophila* use their spores to initiate infection either by adhering to the body of the nematodes or by being ingested and then penetrating the gastrointestinal tract. These fungal species have been reported to parasitize cyst nematode [10].

Plant-Parasitic and Entomopathogenic Nematode Interactions

Some entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) species (e.g., *Steinernema carpocapsae*, *S. feltiae*, *S. riobraveare*, *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora*, *Xenorhabdus nematophilus*) are better known than PPNs and are widely used to manage insect pests in agro-ecosystems [3]. Few studies have observed EPNs to be antagonistic to PPNs and consequently suppress them under field or greenhouse conditions.

Host Plant Resistance

Host resistance is often the most cost-effective tool for nematode management for organic farming systems. Resistant plants are defined as those that support lower levels of nematode reproduction compared to susceptible plants [15], and the extent of nematode-resistant crop varieties has been reviewed [16]. Progress has been made in identifying genes for resistance to the economically important nematode species [25]. These include the Hs1pro-1 gene that provides resistance to the sugar beet cyst nematode (*Heterodera schachtii*), the Mi gene that affects several species of root-knot nematodes in *Meloidogyne*, and the Gpa2 gene that confers resistance against some isolates of the potato cyst nematode (*Globodera pallida*) [24].

CONCLUSION

Crop protection approaches differ widely among organic growers both globally and regionally, yet organic farming faces the same plant-parasitic nematode (PPN) issues as conventional farming. Due to the restrictions on the use of synthetic chemical inputs and the limited number of options for nematode management in organic fields, organic producers are often at greater risk of nematode problems than their conventional counterparts. Resistant cultivars of selective crops are usually resistant to only a few races or species of nematodes and may not last long due to the development of new races over time. Biological control measures involving the use of microbial pathogens, endophytes, and antagonists may play an important role in nematode management in organic crop production, but have shown limited success in their management at a commercial level due to higher cost, and their application may not be yet feasible in large-scale farming systems. A combined approach is needed for nematode management in organic farming systems. Measures such as appropriate crop rotation with less susceptible crop species and green manure crops, soil amendments with antagonistic crops, and consistent weed control are effective when used in together in concert [6]. A combined approach is needed for nematode management in organic farming systems. Measures such as appropriate crop rotation with less susceptible crop species and green manure crops, soil amendments with antagonistic crops, and consistent weed control are effective when used in together in concert [6]. Identification of prevalent PPN species through nematode diagnostic services should be considered for choosing non-hosts before planning long-term crop rotation for organic farming.

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